

Title: Demonstration of All Optical NAND Logic Gate using Photonic Integrated Circuits

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INTRODUCTION:

A novel dual wavelength operated all optical logic operations are demonstrated. The method makes use of bi-directional coupler with unequal lengths of waveguide. The truth table corresponding to the simulated results establishes a NAND logic operation. Since the logic operations are performed with all optical circuits, ultrafast operations of the order of few hundreds of THz could be a possible with the present method.

AIM:

NAND logic gate is one of the important logic gate since it is a universal gate. So this will be solution for the ultrafast computing method or logical operation.

THEORY AND DESIGN

Figure 1 The dual channel optical waveguide used as NAND gate.

We considered a dual channel optical waveguide as shown in Figure 1. Two Y-channels are connected back to back. The ports 1 and 2 act as input ports while the either one of the output ports 3 or 4 act as logic output corresponding to input. Light from Port 1 and 2 is splitted by frustrated total internal reflection. The 2×2 bi-directional coupler are having a path length difference of L . This value of L is equal to the half of wavelength, which we are using as logic 1. Because of this L , constructive and destructive interference are occurring inside the directional coupler, which causes the output to change.

Accordingly, we design the following logic for the demonstration of NAND gate.

- 1) Let us call optical signals of wavelengths λ_1 and λ_2 corresponding to bits '0' and '1'.
- 2) When at ports 1 or 2, a signal of λ_1 , if applied, the output is obtained in both ports 3 and 4. We call port 3 as the output logic; this gives a finite output, that we call as logic.
- 3) When a signal of λ_1 , if applied at both input ports, the output corresponds to an output of logic '1'.
- 4) On the other hand if an input of λ_2 is applied at both ports 1 and 2, the output at port 3 corresponds to logic of '0' as represented in Fig. 2d. This is due to the additional path difference of $\lambda_2/2$ added to port 2.

RESULTS:

As discussed above, the operation of using appropriate λ_1 and λ_2 generates a truth table

Port 1	Port 2	Port 3	Port 1	Port 2	Port 3
λ_1	λ_1	Maxima	0	0	1
λ_1	λ_2	Maxima	0	1	1
λ_2	λ_1	Maxima	1	0	1
λ_2	λ_2	Minima	1	1	0

corresponding to a NAND as described in Table 1.

Table 1 Truth table of NAND Logic.

CONCLUSIONS:

In conclusion we proposed a novel method for all optical logic operation using simple bi-directional coupler with unequal length of waveguide. The simulated result shows that the logic operation is possible. The truth table established shows the NAND logic operation. Since the logic operations are performed with all optical circuits without the help of any electronic system, ultrafast operations of the order of hundreds of THz could be possible

BIOGRAPHY:

Rajeev Chaubey has completed his M. Tech. at the age of 26 years from SGSITS Indore MP, India. He is working as laser engineer since last 4 years in research department of Suresh Indu Lasers Pvt. Ltd. He worked in National MEMS Design Center, Department of Applied Physics, Shri G S Institute of Technology, Indore, a reputational institute for research in the physics and optics. He has published 4 papers in reputed journals.